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D7.2 Report on metrics for data reduction and compression.

Abbreviations

MX	Macromolecular crystallography (single crystal diffraction)
SX	Serial crystallography
XPCS	X-ray photon correlation spectroscopy
S(W)AXS	Small and wide-angle X-ray scattering
HVS	Human Vision System
IQA	Image Quality Assessment
AZINT	Azimuthal Integration

Introduction

This report aims at summarising the different initiatives that have been undertaken regarding the use of relevant metrics in play during data compression. The focus has been put on photon-facility techniques that generate large amounts of data such as macromolecular (serial) crystallography, micro-tomography or time-series diffraction experiments. The underlying structure of the data in each case is very different and in the case of lossy data compression, one needs to objectively measure the impact of such treatment on the scientific quality of the final data, be it a protein structure, a reconstructed tomographic volume or anything else. Evaluating the level degradation on the final outcome often involves expert knowledge qualitative assessment but can nevertheless be often embedded in a few key metrics, reviewed in this document.

Generic data compression metrics (lossless and lossy)

Introduction

Large research infrastructures, such as synchrotron or X-ray free-electron laser facilities, generate large amounts of data (up to a few tens of terabytes for the former to several petabytes for the latter) every day. This data is very valuable as it is the result of elaborate scientific experiments which are likely to be performed only once.

Storing this data efficiently in addition to previously accumulated data, being able to transfer it quickly, and accessing it efficiently for visualisation and scientific analysis is both a necessity and a challenge that digital data compression can address.

Digital data compression consists in reducing the number of bits of the original data while keeping its integrity and, if not, most of its quality.

Lossless and lossy data compression

Compression can be either lossless or lossy. Losslessly compressed data can be decompressed to exactly its original value. Mathematically, this can be expressed as follows: $D(C(s)) = s$, where s is the input signal and C and D the compression and decompression steps, respectively. Lossy compression consists of a transform to separate important (si) from unimportant (su) data, followed generally by lossless compression of the important part and discarding the rest (unimportant data are those that fall outside the human perception and doesn't affect the scientific quality of the data). Mathematically, it can be written as follows: $s = si + su$ and $D(C(si)) = si \approx s$.

In accelerator-based photon source facilities, scientists are generally very reluctant to lose and/or throw away data, since all of them are potentially useful, even decisive, at some point for a reason or another. For this reason, we can say that lossless data compression is much more important than lossy data compression. Besides, it might seem odd to develop more and more powerful detectors (with more pixels, higher sampling rate and/or extra dimension) and do lossy compression right after. Lossy data compression is very useful when critical results are needed quickly in a workflow or to facilitate analysis of scientific data once the data has been acquired. In some situations, the amount of data

generated by the equipment is so large that lossy compression becomes unavoidable, but it is then a great responsibility to set the acceptable loss level.

Raw metrics

Compression can be characterised by three raw metrics: the **compression ratio**, the **compression speed** and the **decompression speed**.

The **compression ratio**, R , is the ratio between the number of bits between the uncompressed data size and compressed data size (Note that some authors use the opposite convention). It is therefore a number theoretically larger than 1. It depends on the:

- strategy used to compress (e.g., sliding window, dictionary, etc.);
- understanding of the data (spatial or temporal structure, noise, etc.);
- memory size.

Instead of the compression ratio, people are sometimes mentioning another metric: namely, the **compression factor**, F , which is defined as the inverse of the compression ratio and is expressed in terms of percentage. Another quoted quantity is the **storage space savings**, S , defined as $1 - 1/R$ and also expressed in percentage.

The **compression speed**, V_c , is the number of bits that are processed per unit of time during compression (and similarly for the **decompression speed**, V_d). It depends on the:

- hardware (i.e., CPU core, bus and memory access speeds; the number of cores);
- algorithm implementation details (data structures used in the program, algorithmic complexity of the involved operations, etc.);
- bandwidth.

It is important to note that the values of V_c or V_d are highly dependent on the type of hardware being used and, potentially, on what is happening on it during the performance testing. This is not the case for the compression ratio, which is a rather stable value, almost independent of the equipment used (its value could be slightly affected by the size of the memory available for the concerned methods).

Obviously, storage requires a large compression ratio: the more compact the data, the less storage space it takes up. But time should also be considered as well. Indeed, if compression takes time, it will not necessarily be of interest.

Time-related metrics

Let's take the concrete example of a user who wants to transfer some data over the network. A compression/decompression cycle is interesting in terms of time if the cumulative time for compressing the original file, transferring the compressed data and decompressing the compressed data is lower than the time to transfer the original file. Writing this condition leads to the following inequality: $\vartheta t < 1$, where $\vartheta t = Vt/V_c + 1/R + Vt/V_d$ with Vt being the transfer speed. It suffices that one of these terms is larger than 1 to break the inequality. In particular, we want $V_c > Vt$ which shows that V_c is a limiting factor. But remember, regardless of any temporal consideration, data compression is only useful if $R > 1$.

If compression is indeed interesting (i.e., $\vartheta t < 1$), the next step is to determine which algorithm to choose. Given two compression techniques (indices 1 and 2), one must compare the time taken by each of them to compress, transfer and decompress the data. In other words, one just has to compute the term ϑt for each algorithm (ϑt_1 and ϑt_2) and pick the smallest value. Note however that if storage and fast transmission are considered part of the same problem (i.e. having both a large R and V_c), then the criterion can be relaxed and one can choose the compression algorithm characterised by the largest R with a reasonably small value of ϑt (but still lower than 1).

Another frequently encountered scenario is when compression and decompression are considered as two separate phases. Such a situation occurs when backing up data to an external hard disk, or when reading and writing HDF5 files with compression activated, or when accessing file systems working with compression. Writing the time constraints with the same reasoning as before, we obtain the following metric in the case of compression (usually performed once): $\vartheta w < 1$, where $\vartheta w = V_w/V_c + 1/R$ with V_w being the writing speed. Similarly, the time constraint in the case of decompression (usually performed several times) gives rise to the following inequality: $\vartheta r < 1$, where $\vartheta r = 1/R + V_r/V_d$, with V_r being the reading speed. However, we recall that first and foremost data compression is only useful if $R > 1$.

Generic lossless compressors and their performance

Many compressors have been developed since the late 1970s. The best known and most used are:

- gzip/zlib (1991, Jean-Loup Gailly, Mark Adler);
- deflate (1996, Phil Katz);
- bzip2 (1996, Julien Seward);
- lzma or xz (1996, Igor Pavlov, Lasse Collin);
- lz4 (2011, Yann Collet at Google);
- snappy (2011, Google);
- brotli (2013, Jyrki Alakuijala and Zoltan Szabadka at Google);
- zstd (2015, Yann Collet at Facebook).

A good way to evaluate the performance of the various compressors is to present the results in the (R, V_c) plane. If the characteristics of the network or system are known, it could be also interesting to plot the performance results in the $(R, \vartheta t)$ or $(R, \vartheta w)$ or $(R, \vartheta r)$ plane.

The compressors which give the best results in terms of speed and compression ratio are the most recent ones, namely lz4 and zstd. In general, they have V_c of the order of 0.5 to 1 GB/s and V_d of the order of 1 to 5 GB/s. Zstd is particularly interesting as it is multi-threaded at compression (but not decompression). If several cores are used, zstd can be faster than the mono-threaded lz4 compressor (Note however that there is no clear relation between the number of cores used and the compression speed; in general, it is much more complicated than a simple linear scaling). Several compressors such as pbzip2, pigz and pixz (i.e., parallelized versions of bzip2, gzip and xz, respectively) are multi-threaded at both compression and decompression, but are characterised by a very low compression

and decompression speeds (at least an order of magnitude lower compared to zstd and lz4). In terms of compression ratio, zstd provides consistently better results than lz4. However, the highest compression ratios are obtained with compressors developed solely for the purpose of having a large R , regardless of time. These are bzip2 and lzma/xz.

Compressors have generally tunable parameters, among which the compression level is one of the most important. Each compressor has its own range of levels. For instance lz4 has compression levels ranging from 1 to 9, while zstd has levels ranging from 1 to 22. Low compression levels are close to real time (i.e. as fast as the data can be acquired and written to storage), whereas higher compression levels take more CPU time (V_c decreases) and especially do not necessarily bring significant improvement in the compression ratio, R . We recommend systematically using the lowest compression levels as a first step to at least ensure that the compression is effective. If the lower levels don't work, the higher levels are unlikely to work.

Of course, the compression ratio that can be reached will strongly depend on the data (Is it noisy? Is it mostly empty? etc.). The most difficult data to compress are in general projection images (also known as radiographs) from tomography experiments, which are characterised by very delicate and faint structures immersed in a very fine-grained (if not noisy) background. In general, the compression ratios obtained are of the order of 1 (compression failed) to 1.5 at maximum. Reconstructed volumes from these projection scans have compression ratios between roughly 1.5 and 2. On the other hand, data coming from X-ray diffraction beamlines (producing sparse data) are easily compressed with a compression ratio of the order of 20 to 60.

Improving data compression

There are several ways to improve the efficiency of the above codecs. A classical solution to reach a larger compression ratio consists in rearranging the internal structure of the data by shuffling the data at the bit or byte level (e.g., bitshuffle by Kyo Masui [BITSHUFFLE], c-blosc2 [C-BLOSC2]). Obviously, this introduces additional delays in the balance, since we have to take into account the time for transforming the raw data (shuffle) and the compressed data (unshuffle), but in general, it has proven to be an efficient tool. For improving the compression speed, multi-threading is a powerful technique: data is split into chunks, chunks are compressed in parallel and merged at the end. Of course, any combination of the above can be successful. In particular, the C-Blosc orchestrator (version 1 [C-BLOSC] or version 2 [C-BLOSC2]), which combines a clever use of the characteristics of the memory hierarchical model (i.e., L1, L2 and/or L3 CPU caches) to optimise memory I/O, along with shuffling and multi-threading, has proven to provide very good results for many different codecs (lz4, zstd, etc.).

External versus integrated data compression

There are two different strategies for using data compression. The first one consists in using the codecs via the command line on a single file or, when it is possible, on a set of files. The second approach is to integrate the compression within the file format/container: in general, the codecs are applied to a portion of the data (the so-called chunks). A good example is provided by the HDF5 file format and its compression filters [HDF5FILTER] such as those provided by the hdf5plugin [HDF5PLUGIN] Python

library. It allows the use of several compressors (among which lz4 and zstd) as well as bit/byte-shuffling pre-filtering, and possibly through the C-Blosc orchestrator. One of the advantages of this approach is that one can work with compressed data (so smaller files assuming that the compression has been effective) and yet one can load and decompress very quickly only the part of the data that interests you (i.e., without decompressing the whole file). A strong constraint however is that the size and shape (e.g. row, column or block) of the chunks has to be fixed before writing the data and applying the compression.

Ease of use

From an end user point of view, the hardware requirements (e.g., GPU) and ease of installation are also essential. It is fine to have complex compression pipelines at large facilities, where dedicated staff can ensure they work smoothly. From the user point of view (the scientist community at large with a wide range of computing proficiency), any compression scheme should be transparent, and implemented in the data analysis and visualisation software, or it will not be suitable for general use. As an example, a compression algorithm already provided by the data file format (e.g., GZIP in HDF5) is easier to use and so more likely to be widely used than one provided as a plugin of the file format that the user first need to compile and install before being able to use it. This is the reason behind developments such as hdf5plugin [HDF5PLUGIN] which provide different codecs transparently.

Benchmarking

Evaluating the compression algorithm performance is a particularly delicate exercise for the following reasons:

- Compression and decompression are usually tested on the same machine for convenience, but one and the other could happen in different places in real life;
- It would be desirable to work in an isolated and clean computing environment (e.g., clean memory caches) to obtain intrinsic and robust measures on V_c and V_d , but these would still remain overestimates compared to what would happen in real conditions of use;
- Compressing large volume of data (tens of GB) can be quite long (up to an hour or so), especially for the highest levels of compression (which, moreover, may not bring any significant improvement in terms of R) and/or for compressors developed solely for the purpose of having large R , regardless of time;
- Results are only valid for the dataset used for the performance tests;
- Running the tests several times to obtain statistics on V_c and V_d is questionable given the above points. Gaussian distributions should not be expected.

Finally, we recommend applying the following general principle to reduce the ecological/economical footprint: test less, test better.

Source codes for running performance tests

Tools have been developed for benchmarking, which are freely available here:

<https://gitlab.com/soleil-data-treatment/soleil-software-projects>

More precisely, we provide:

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- lzbench-toolbox: bash scripts to use lzbench [LZBENCH] (an in-memory benchmark of open-source LZ77/LZSS/LZMA compressors);
- codec-bench: bash scripts to obtain the metrics associated with compression and decompression (i.e., R , V_c , V_d). It outputs CSV files similarly to lzbench, but it includes compressors with multi-threading capabilities. The compressors currently implemented are: bzip2, gzip, lz4, pbzip2, pigz, pixz, xz, zstd;
- blosc-codec-bench: C program which runs performance tests on 32-bit floating-point binary files using C-Blosc2. The supported compressors are: blosclz, lz4, lz4hc, zlib, zstd;
- codec-bench-analysis: Python scripts to plot, analyse and print the results from lzbench-toolbox and codec-bench.

Data reduction metrics for azimuthal integration (powder diffraction and small/wide angle scattering)

Photon counting and charge integrating area (2D) detectors are the most common instruments for recording photons in scattering experiments at photon sources, including powder diffraction. They allow a maximum solid-angle coverage, high detection efficiency and time resolution. In order to simplify data analysis, a 2D detector image is traditionally reduced into a 1D pattern in radial space (e.g. scattering length q -space or 2θ scattering angle). The reduced 1D data are often sufficient for accurate interpretation of the experiment. The transformation for the case of digital data originating from modern photon detectors is called “azimuthal integration” (AZINT) since it produces average values of pixel intensities along rings on the detector image. Detector images are initially several megapixels in size and azimuthal integration can reduce the amount of data by a factor of ~ 1000 , but the stored volume is less compressed due to the change of data-type (floating-point values compress less than integers). AZINT itself is not a compression but a data reduction technique, yielding the 1D pattern which is relevant for the analysis by users. It is also a sophisticated data transformation that strongly depends on other **metadata**, in particular a set of parameters describing the geometry of the experiment - so called “**calibration**”, and often multiple **corrections of measured intensities** are applied. The corrections include among others: solid angle, polarization, sample, parallax and oblique incidence angle effect corrections. Number of points (bins) of the reduced 1D pattern grid and its range are additional adjustable AZINT parameters. Detector gain must be known for charge integrating detectors or another method of evaluating the counting statistics should be available. AZINT can also introduce correlations between neighbouring bins of the resulting pattern [Yang2014] and so additional data may need to be stored for estimating standard uncertainties and for further data analysis. The quantitative data analysis of photon scattering experiments is usually based on refining a structural model to fit the reduced scattering data in a maximum likelihood sense [McCusker1999, Toby2013]. This requires compressed or reduced data to preserve their statistical characteristics (**estimated standard uncertainties and correlation coefficients**).

Azimuthal integration is by nature a lossy data reduction method. However the information loss is minimised if the sample scattering is isotropic. This is a very common case in certain types of experiments, in particular biological SAXS and conventional powder diffraction, and it is further

improved by instrumental techniques, in particular sample spinning. Whereas for some experiments data reduction by AZINT is valued, for other classes of experiments, when the nature of the measurement relies on anisotropy in the sample scattering, the AZINT procedure applied to the whole detector image is unacceptable as all the relevant information may be lost. Sometimes a compromise is possible. The detector image can be divided into multiple parts and AZINT can be applied on them individually. In such a model case, the user can decide to extract e.g. 18 times 1D patterns from different parts of the detector. The user can also require to store estimated experimental data uncertainties and so the potential data reduction ratio from the example above (~ 1000) can be effectively reduced by the factor of $18 * 2$ and the overall data reduction ratio ~ 30 is not so great. This demonstrates that the data **reduction ratio**, defined as the ratio of raw unreduced data volume and the final reduced data volume including metadata for evaluating quality of the result, is an important metric also for AZINT.

Reduced 1D patterns are very often analysed later with least-square-fitting or global-optimization methods [McCusker1999, Toby2013, Yang2014] and the quality of the result is usually evaluated in terms of **R-values**, in particular the weighted-profile R value, R_{wp} , and the statistically expected R value, R_{exp} , [McCusker1999]. If the number of parameters of the structural model is much lower than the number of data points of the reduced 1D pattern, which is often the case, R_{exp} can be evaluated directly from the data and reflects their quality (counting statistics). Evaluating R_{wp} is more complex as it assumes the final result of the data analysis is known. However both R -values are of interest as they can indicate possible issues in data treatment and it is evident that different data reduction procedures giving reasonable analysis results and similar R -values are providing similar quality of the final results to the user.

It is worth mentioning a few more practical aspects of reducing data with AZINT. To achieve the data volume reduction, raw detector images must be discarded, i.e. not saved but this was not done until recently for two main reasons: 1. a wrong detector geometry calibration jeopardises the complete data reduction; 2. rebinning and merging of several datasets was not possible. However in many cases the community accepts that the AZINT reduction is robust enough, and the 2D raw data can be discarded, the 1D scattering pattern being considered as the effective raw data. This is particularly true for small/wide-angle scattering where the useful pixel resolution is not very high. Several graphical user interfaces have been developed to provide scientists with reliable geometry calibration for their experiments [DAWN, PYFAI, Ilavsky2012, Toby2013] in order to address the former point. Recent development [BIOSAXS22] demonstrated it was possible to rebin data and/or merge several datasets when the summed signal and normalisation were persisted. Uncertainties can also be propagated accordingly [Yang2014, BIOSAXS22] which addresses the second issue.

One example of data volume reduction: a single frame of an Eiger9M weights 39 MB and the associated powder diffraction pattern only 127 kB which represents a reduction ratio of 314 while preserving metadata and allowing it to be rebinned on a coarser grid, if needed.

In spite of many external parameters entering the AZINT data reduction, AZINT can be interpreted often as a (sparse) matrix multiplication and highly optimised libraries (Intel MKL, CuPy, PyTorch, TensorFlow etc.) can be used. There are also specific optimised AZINT codes utilising compute hardware accelerators (one example is PyFAI [PYFAI]). In the case the user accepts discarding raw 2D detector data, AZINT reduction can be implemented close to the detector. This is minimising required network bandwidth, energy costs and allowing very high throughput experiments. The latter case can benefit from effective AZINT implementations and so the data **reduction speed**, defined as a number of reduced image pixels per unit time, presents a relevant metric.

Sparse data reduction (XPCS / coherent X-ray scattering)

XPCS provides information about dynamics in condensed matter, by doing X-ray scattering with a coherent beam and analysing fluctuations in the resulting speckle pattern. To study dynamics on short timescales, correspondingly high detector frame rates are required, but the resulting images are typically sparse, with most pixels in the detector recording 0 photons or 1 photon. Photon-counting detectors are normally used for these experiments, to allow high speed and noise-free operation.

Under these conditions, lossless compression methods already achieve high compression ratios. For example, if raw images are in 8-bit format but most pixels are 0 or 1, then after a bitshuffle filter is applied there will be long runs of bytes with value 0, corresponding to the zero-valued upper bits. This can then be compressed by relatively simple algorithms like LZ4. Conversely, the distinction between having 0 or 1 photon in a pixel is crucial to analysis, so there's little potential for lossy compression. With lossless compression, the only quality metric required is that decompressed images must be identical to the original. However, the high frame rate in these experiments means that high compression and decompression speed is the most important requirement.

There is also a trend towards reducing data by processing it during the experiment [Narayanan 2022]. In XPCS, data processing consists of calculating per-pixel autocorrelation functions over time (describing speckle fluctuations) and typically averaging these as a function of angle. Libraries for this using hardware acceleration with OpenCL [Paleo2021] have been developed for this. Once again, computing performance is the key requirement.

Combining these points, it has been demonstrated that if most of the pixels in an XPCS dataset are zero, then it can be advantageous to represent the data as a list of nonzero pixels (with pixel index and count value) [Zhang2021]. This representation can not only achieve a good compression ratio, but it can also be used directly in calculating autocorrelations without the need to convert back to a full image. So, it is important to consider the speed of the full processing chain when comparing compression methods. As the XPCS technique can operate on a wide speed range (from $\ll 1$ Hz to more than 1 MHz), the most relevant metric is the compression speed, which could e.g. be achieved using dedicated hardware such as FPGA [MADDEN2011]

Data reduction for imaging (lossy or not, 2D and 3D)

Image Quality Assessment (IQA) [Thung2009] is a vast active research area, aiming at predicting perceived image quality by human observers [Athar2019]. Quality measures inspired by the **Human Vision System (HVS)** represent state of the art [Wang2009, Athar2019, Sampat2009]. This report focuses on full-reference metrics [Pedersen2012], where two images are compared.

Conventional pixel-based metrics are based on norms; by expressing two images x and y as two monodimensional vectors, the **Minkowski metric** [Thung2009] can be used to derive many expressions that consider the dissimilarity between the two, e.g. the **Mean Absolute Error (MAE)** or the **Mean Squared Error (MSE)**. This kind of pixel-wise metrics offer several advantages [Wang2009], including ease of use and clear physical meaning. It has been consistently demonstrated, however, that these metrics have a weak association with perceptual image quality [Wang2009]. **Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR)** is another frequently used alternative and currently represents the “gold standard” [Athar2019]. While it is useful for images having different bit-depths, it provides no new information compared to MSE [Wang2009, Athar2019]. These metrics can be implemented very quickly in any programming language or through the scikit-image [skimagequality] and the OpenCV [OpenCVquality] libraries that provide stable, mature and verified implementations.

Structural Similarity (SSIM) [Wang2009] is one of the most used HVS metrics defined to measure the similarity of local image “structures”, often using correlation measures. The prototype is the **Universal Image Quality Index (UQI)** index [Wang2002], which combines similarity measures of three conceptually independent components - luminance, contrast and structure. Implementations of this quality index are very common in scikit-image [skimagequality], TensorFlow [tensorflow_image] and PyTorch [pytorch_metrics]. Even if considered a *de facto* standard, many authors found a deterministic link between PSNR and SSIM (e.g. in [Hore2010]), arguing about its performances. To solve the drawbacks of the prototype SSIM, multiple measures have been proposed such as **MS-SSIM** [Wang2003] (**Multi-Scale extension**) or **CW-SSIM** [Wang2005] (**Complex Wavelet SSIM index**), which in turn are invariant to multiple scales and small geometric transformations. Open-source python implementations are also readily available, e.g. in [pytorch_metrics, IQA-opt, tensorflow_image].

Just Noticeable Distortion (JND)-based visually lossless compression is defined as the maximum visibility threshold before lossy compression distortions become perceptually discernible to the Human Visual System (HVS) [Prangnell2018]. New IQA methods exploit indeed an arbitrary complete psychophysical model which takes into account the **Contrast Sensitivity Function (CSF)**, the **luminance contrast sensitivity** and the **contrast masking** [Hore2010] of the HVS in order to estimate how pixel-level differences are visible to the human eye. A form of image decomposition based on wavelets or cosine transform is typically employed to describe the HVS behaviour. In the following text, many examples will be presented; the **VIF index** [Sheikh2006] is based upon the assumption that any subband from the test image can be expressed as the linear combination of the corresponding subband from the reference image. The resultant metric estimates the amount of information lost

from a reference image as a result of distortion. Open-source implementations are available in [sewar][vifpython][IQA-python].

The **Visual Signal-to-Noise Ratio (VSNR)** [Chandler2007] also operates on image decompositions: at first, the contrast threshold for distortion is evaluated on the wavelet transform: if under a certain threshold, the test image is deemed to be indistinguishable from the reference, thus disclosing perfect visual fidelity (VSNR = infinity). If the distortion is above the threshold, a second process evaluates the perceived contrast and mid-level visual properties of the two images [Lin2011]. An open-source python implementation is deployed in [vsnrpython].

The **HDRVDP** [Mantiuk2005], is an extension of **Visual Difference Predictor** [Daly1993], specially designed for HDR images. The HDRVDP has been reported to accurately reproduce radiologists' perception of compression artefacts in CT images [Kim2008a, Kim2008b, Kim2008c, Kim2008d, Kim2010]. Being a full reference quality index, HDRVDP takes two images as input and then generates a probability-of-detection map in which the pixel value indicates the probability that an observer viewing the two images will detect the difference at that pixel location [Mantiuk2005]. Similarly to the mean SSIM (MSSIM), the map can be summarised into a single value representing the overall perceptual image fidelity. Open-source implementations of the algorithm exist but only in C++ and Matlab. A Python wrapper has thus been recently deployed by Elettra SciComp [elettrascicompwrapper].

Among all the presented metrics if applied on large-scale datasets, currently, no measure is really outstanding compared to the others. Best results are obtained by a mixture of many quality measures processed by machine-learning-based regressors, e.g. the **Video Multi-Method Assessment Fusion (VMAF)** algorithm [Sinno2019] developed by Netflix as an open source development kit [vmafpython]. This approach typically involves subjective judgement provided by human expert operators, in the form of labels for the supervised learning procedure of quality regressor. Regarding clinical CT compression, in [Nam2018] a similar approach has been used to train a linear regressor whose inputs are both metadata from the datasets and other full-reference image metrics.

In conclusion, it appears that for natural images (e.g. Netflix) the VIF index seems to fit best (being the core of VMAF), while in a different study IWSSIM [Wang2022], FSIMc [Zhang2022] and VSI [Zhang2014], are considered "the top performers". Regarding CT, in the present literature, HDRVDP appears as a good candidate. However, also the latest variants of the SSIM (4-MS-g-r* [Renieblas2017]) are reported to be in agreement with a human radiologist [Renieblas2017]. The new libjpegl source code [libjpegl] provides an extensive test suite that can be taken as an example workflow to estimate many indexes.

List of quality indexes employed for CT compression studies (both clinical/microscopy):

Reference	Employed quality metrics
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[Kim2010]	PSNR, MSSIM, HDRVDP
[Gokbay2013]	PSNR, MSE
[Nam2018]	MSE, PSNR, HDRVDP
[Mancini2018]	MSE, PSNR, SSIM
[Yan2019]	PSNR, MSE
[Marone2020]	SSIM

IQA Software implementations:

Software Library	Methods
[OpenCVquality]	BRISQUE (Blind/Referenceless Image Spatial Quality Evaluator), GMSD, MSE, PSNR, SSIM
[skimagequality]	Normalised Mutual Information (NMI), NRMSE, PSNR, SSIM,
[tensorflow_image]	PSNR, SSIM, MS-SSIM
[IQA-opt]	SSIM, MS-SSIM, CW-SSIM, FSIM, VSI, GMSD, NLPD, MAD, VIF, LPIPS, DIST.
[pytorch_metrics]	SSIM, MS-SSIM, PSNR, Spectral Angle Mapper (SAM), UQI
[hdrvdpsf], [hdrvdpgit], [elettrasciompwrapper]	HDRVDP
[vsnrpython]	VSNR
[vifpython]	VIF
[sewar]	MSE, RMSE, PSNR, SSIM, UQI, MS-SSIM, VIF

Data reduction for serial crystallography

As mentioned earlier in this report, X-ray diffraction techniques, and macromolecular crystallography (MX) in particular produce very sparse raw-data images and are well suited for lossless data compression approaches. Traditionally, after raw images are acquired, a data-reduction procedure is systematically performed to integrate, scale and merge the signal contained in the Bragg spots, turning a several GB raw-dataset into a list of intensities or amplitudes with a size of a few MB. This however, is not considered data compression since the raw data is always preserved in the likely case that a

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reprocessing need arises (for example an initial bad indexing can lead to a wrong hypothesis concerning the underlying space-group and lead to merge reflections that should have been kept separate).

The rise of serial-crystallography (SX) in both synchrotrons and XFEL facilities resulted in a dramatic increase in the size of the raw data produced (in the TB to PB range per experiment) due to the very high number of images produced (up to 2 kHz with multi-megapixel detector on synchrotron beamlines, i.e. above 10 GB/s) and the ever-increasing image resolution. Two orthogonal approaches to reduce the size of the raw-data, prior to the traditional data reduction procedure aforementioned, are currently employed or being developed:

1 - **Triage** - rejecting immediately images bearing no relevant signal, is essential: in a SX experiment, typically between 30 to 90% of diffraction frames can either present no diffraction, or too few peaks to allow indexing the image, in which case the data should also be discarded. In both cases the difficulty relies on the speed at which the evaluation must be done, which is easy in the absence of diffraction, but the evaluation of frames which cannot be indexed will require the implementation of faster algorithms, e.g. using parallel programming on GPUs.

2 - **Mixed-compression approach**, which consists in discriminating the signal contained in the Bragg peaks (region of interest, ROI) from the background area on each image and apply different compression treatment to each (i.e. the Bragg peak signal undergoes lossless compression while the background will use a lossy compression).

While the first approach (triage) is often used in real-time during SX data acquisition, the second approach is still recent and several methods are being developed. The key in this case is to examine the traditional metrics used during all the steps from raw data processing to structure refinement to examine their sensibility to lossy compression. This was performed in a recent study [Underwood2022] in which a peak finder is used to isolate the region of interest (ROI: rectangular region around the peaks) from the background. The ROI represents between 1% and 5% of the data to be compressed, which is in this case performed in a lossless fashion. Fpzip [FPZIP], a specialised compressor for floating-point values seems to give the best performance in this case. The region identified as non-ROI (95% to 99% of the data to be compressed) is submitted to **binning followed by lossy compression** (testing different algorithms: SZ, SZ2, SZ3, MGARD, ZFP, BLOSC, SZ is retained in the end). In this case, three key parameters affect the compression ratio:

- **Binning** : dimension of the window of 2D data to compress (i.e. 3x3 averages 9 values together) → 2x2 gave the best results.
- **Tolerance** : Maximum absolute pointwise error allowed during lossy compression of the binned values → proportional to the detector readout for a single photon (45 ADU - analogue to digital - units) so the search was conducted for 10 and 90 ADU.
- **Dimension** : dimension in which adjacent features in the data are used by the SZ algorithm. 1D, 2D, 3D

The traditional MX metrics (after integration, scaling and merging) were then examined with and without this compression method:

- R_{split} : deviation between two halves of a dataset, which are theoretically identical (because of central symmetry in the reciprocal space), although a bit divergent when there is anomalous signal, it should remain below 20%
- $CC_{1/2}$ measures the same thing as R_{split} but using a Pearson correlation coefficient

The two last metrics are available as soon as the dataset has been reduced, and allow us to know early whether there is a fundamental problem with the data or not. For example if we chose the wrong point group in the indexing phase.

Indicators measuring the agreement between model and experimental data:

After amplitudes have been obtained, phasing and refinement are performed, allowing to build a molecular model in the density so that it fits the data. The indicators are **R-factors** that measure the deviation between the data (amplitudes) that would be generated (back-Fourier-transformed) by our model alone and the experimental amplitudes.

- R_{work} : agreement between current protein model and data (amplitudes). It can be prone to overfitting since we make the model stick to the experimental data.
- R_{free} : same thing as R_{work} but the experimental data were kept apart and NOT used in model building (usually 5 to 10% of the data)

R_{free} is one of the most impactful metrics for reviewers, to know whether the "structure was solved". One generally tries to have both R_{work} and R_{free} below 20%. R_{free} is often a bit higher than R_{work} at the end.

Indicators to measure the quality of the anomalous signal:

- CC_{anom} : correlation coefficient between the anomalous differences (when the symmetry of your space group allows it). The higher the better, usually 0.1% (less than 0.04 is considered a low anomalous signal for Selenium).

Other indicators used to compare original and compressed data:

- **Peak-to-signal ratio (PSNR)** of the merged intensities
- **Mean percentage error (MPE)** of the merged intensities

The question of lossy compression for MX/SX is elegantly formulated by J. Holton in his blog¹ as: "how much compression can you apply before the amplitudes change by more than the value of their standard deviation?". As we saw, traditional data processing metrics focus on internal consistency in a dataset and do not allow to detect data degradation. It is therefore desirable to use inter-dataset

¹ https://bl831.als.lbl.gov/~jamesh/lossy_compression/

metrics (such as MPE here or inter-dataset R-factors) on training data in order to calibrate the compression parameters that can be applied in various experimental contexts.

As a conclusion, it is important to note that the use of mixed lossless/lossy compression for SX is fairly new, and will remain a research topic in the years to come - a key element will be to evaluate how much information can be lost notably from high resolution data where it can be difficult to distinguish peaks from the background.

Final words - metrics, acceptability and pipelines

In this report we have seen a wide range of data compression and reduction which are available for the different techniques. The metrics associated with those range from generic ones (compression ratio and speed), while more complex ones are required for lossy compression schemes, and need to evaluate what scientifically relevant information has been lost. In that respect, the role of scientific communities and bodies (such as the International Union for Crystallography) cannot be underestimated as 'acceptable' loss of information must be clearly defined, notably to ensure the reliability and the reproducibility of our analysis techniques.

The other aspect which is essential when defining metrics for data quality is the development of **reproducible pipelines** (software, including their version and configuration, hardware used, workflow steps, etc..), associated with **open data**, both of which are part of an Open Science approach. This will be tackled notably as part of task 7.3 in the LEAPS-Innov project.

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